

C Proofs

Hereafter we present sketches of proofs for our theorems. Complete mechanised formalisation of the following results was done in Coq⁸.

► **Lemma 5** (Reflexivity). *For all w , then $w \leq_S w$.*

Proof. To show that $w \leq_S w$ we need to construct a tpestate simulation R such that $(w, w) \in R$.

Let $R = \{(w, w) \mid w \in \mathcal{W}\}$. Clearly $(w, w) \in R$.

To show that R is a tpestate simulation consider $(w_1, w_2) \in R$. This implies that $w_1 = w_2$ and $\text{def}(w_1) = \text{def}(w_2)$. It is then easy to observe that all the conditions in Def. 3 hold. ◀

► **Lemma 6** (Transitivity). *For all $w_1^{E_1}, w_2^{E_2}, w_3^{E_3}$, if $w_1^{E_1} \leq_S w_2^{E_2}$ and $w_2^{E_2} \leq_S w_3^{E_3}$, then also $w_1^{E_1} \leq_S w_3^{E_3}$.*

Proof. Suppose that $w \leq_S w'$ and $w' \leq_S w''$ (with the definitional equations implied). To show $w \leq_S w''$ we need to construct a tpestate simulation R such that $(w, w'') \in R$. Let R_1 and R_2 be tpestate simulations such that $(w, w') \in R_1$ and $(w', w'') \in R_2$ (following from our assumptions and Def. 3).

Let $R = \{(w_1, w_3) \mid \exists w_2, (w_1, w_2) \in R_1 \wedge (w_2, w_3) \in R_2\}$. Clearly $(w, w'') \in R$.

To show that R is a tpestate simulation consider $(w_1, w_3) \in R$. Then there exists w_2 such that $(w_1, w_2) \in R_1$ and $(w_2, w_3) \in R_2$.

If $\text{def}(w_1) = d\{\widetilde{m} : w\}$ then $\text{def}(w_2) = d'\{\widetilde{m}' : w'\}$ and $\text{def}(w_3) = d\{\widetilde{m}'' : w''\}$.

Because R_2 is a tpestate simulation, for all $m:w''$ in $d\{\widetilde{m}'' : w''\}$, there is one w' such that $m:w'$ in $d'\{\widetilde{m}' : w'\}$ and $(w', w'') \in R_2$. Because R_1 is a tpestate simulation, for all $m:w'$ in $d'\{\widetilde{m}' : w'\}$, there is one w such that $m:w$ in $d\{\widetilde{m} : w\}$ and $(w, w') \in R_1$. It follows then that for all $m:w''$ in $d\{\widetilde{m}'' : w''\}$, there is one w such that $m:w$ in $d\{\widetilde{m} : w\}$ and $(w, w'') \in R$. The case (1.a) of Def. 3 is satisfied.

Additionally, $d'' = \text{drop}$ implies $d' = \text{drop}$, and $d' = \text{drop}$ implies $d = \text{drop}$. Clearly $d'' = \text{drop}$ implies $d = \text{drop}$ and the case (1.b) of Def. 3 is satisfied.

The case (2) of Def. 3 is similar. ◀

► **Definition 55** (Algorithm termination measure). *Given the syntax of tpestates (Def. 1) and the fact that the number of equations \widetilde{E} associated with a protocol is finite, the number of tpestates within that protocol is also finite. So, the maximum size of the set Σ is bounded. Consider the measure $\mathbf{m}(\Sigma)$ which is the maximum size of Σ subtracted by the size of Σ .*

► **Lemma 56** (Algorithm termination). *The tpestate subtyping algorithm always terminates.*

Proof. For any goal $\Sigma \vdash w_1 \leq_{S_{atg}} w_2$ either:

- $(w_1, w_2) \in \Sigma$ and the ASSUMP rule is immediately applied, which does not generate new sub-goals;
- $(w_1, w_2) \notin \Sigma$ and either INPUT or OUTPUT are applied. In both cases, sub-goals with smaller measures (Def. 55) than the current goal are generated.

Therefore the algorithm always terminates. ◀

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/7712822>

► **Theorem 8** (Algorithm completeness). *If $w_1^{E_1} \leq_S w_2^{E_2}$ then $\emptyset \vdash w_1^{E_1} \leq_{S_{alg}} w_2^{E_2}$.*

Proof. We generalise the above statement and show that if $w_1 \leq_S w_2$ then $\Sigma \vdash w_1 \leq_{S_{alg}} w_2$ for any Σ by induction on the measure $\mathbf{m}(\Sigma)$ presented in Def. 55.

If $\mathbf{m}(\Sigma) = 0$, then clearly $(w_1, w_2) \in \Sigma$. Therefore, $\Sigma \vdash w_1 \leq_{S_{alg}} w_2$ by the ASSUMP rule.

Otherwise, consider the induction hypothesis

$$\forall \Sigma', w, w' . \mathbf{m}(\Sigma') < \mathbf{m}(\Sigma) \implies w \leq_S w' \implies \Sigma' \vdash w \leq_{S_{alg}} w'$$

If $(w_1, w_2) \in \Sigma$, then we can immediately apply the ASSUMP rule. Otherwise, we need to apply INPUT or OUTPUT. Since $w_1 \leq_S w_2$, there is a tpestate simulation R such that $(w_1, w_2) \in R$ by Def. 4. We now proceed by cases according to Def. 3.

- Case $\mathbf{def}(w_1) = \widetilde{d\{m : w\}}$:
Hypotheses:
 1. $\mathbf{def}(w_2) = \widetilde{d'\{m' : w'\}}$
 2. for all $m:w$ in $\widetilde{d\{m : w\}}$, there is one w such that $m:w$ in $\widetilde{d'\{m' : w'\}}$ and $(w, w') \in R$.
 3. if $d' = \mathbf{drop}$ then $d = \mathbf{drop}$.
 We can now apply the INPUT rule and satisfy the sub-goals of the form $\Sigma, (w_1, w_2) \vdash w \leq_{S_{alg}} w$ by using the induction hypothesis. Therefore, $\Sigma \vdash w_1 \leq_{S_{alg}} w_2$.
 - Case $\mathbf{def}(w_1) = \langle \widehat{o} : \widetilde{u} \rangle$:
Similar to the previous case.
- Therefore, $\Sigma \vdash w_1 \leq_{S_{alg}} w_2$ for any Σ . ◀

► **Lemma 57** (Algorithm with extended Σ). *If $\Sigma \vdash w_1 \leq_{S_{alg}} w_2$ then $\Sigma, \Sigma' \vdash w_1 \leq_{S_{alg}} w_2$ for any Σ' .*

Proof. By induction on the derivation $\Sigma \vdash w_1 \leq_{S_{alg}} w_2$. ◀

► **Theorem 9** (Algorithm soundness). *If $\emptyset \vdash w_1^{E_1} \leq_{S_{alg}} w_2^{E_2}$ then $w_1^{E_1} \leq_S w_2^{E_2}$.*

Proof. To show that $w_1 \leq_S w_2$ we need to construct a tpestate simulation R such that $(w_1, w_2) \in R$.

We say **sound** Σ holds if $\forall (w'', w''') \in \Sigma . \Sigma \setminus (w'', w''') \vdash w'' \leq_{S_{alg}} w'''$.

Let $R = \{(w, w') \mid \exists \Sigma . (w, w') \in \Sigma \wedge \mathbf{sound} \Sigma\}$.

By picking $\Sigma = \emptyset, (w_1, w_2)$ and given our assumption that $\emptyset \vdash w_1 \leq_{S_{alg}} w_2$, we can clearly show that $(w_1, w_2) \in R$.

Now we need to show that R is a tpestate simulation. The intuition is that for $(w, w') \in R$ to hold, it would be enough to find a Σ that contains all the reachable pairs of tpestates. In this case, the goal $\Sigma \setminus (w'', w''') \vdash w'' \leq_{S_{alg}} w'''$ would ensure that all the preliminary subtyping checks (without recursively checking the continuations) hold. Since we would do this for all $(w'', w''') \in \Sigma$, we would “close the cycles” and ensure subtyping holds for the pair (w, w') . We now make the proof more precise.

To show that R is a tpestate simulation consider $(w_3, w_4) \in R$. Therefore, there is a Σ such that $(w_3, w_4) \in \Sigma$, **sound** Σ , and $\Sigma \setminus (w_3, w_4) \vdash w_3 \leq_{S_{alg}} w_4$. We now proceed by cases on how the goal $\Sigma \setminus (w_3, w_4) \vdash w_3 \leq_{S_{alg}} w_4$ was generated.

- Case ASSUMP:
This case is not possible since $(w_3, w_3) \in \Sigma \setminus (w_3, w_4)$ does not hold.

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■ Case INPUT:

Note that $(\Sigma \setminus (w_3, w_4), (w_3, w_4)) = \Sigma$.

Hypotheses:

1. $\mathbf{def}(w_3) = d\{\widetilde{m : w}\}$ and $\mathbf{def}(w_4) = d\{\widetilde{m' : w'}\}$
2. $\forall m:w' \in d\{\widetilde{m' : w'}\} . \exists m:w \in d\{\widetilde{m : w}\} . \Sigma \vdash w \leq_{S_{alg}} w'$
3. $d' = \mathbf{drop} \implies d = \mathbf{drop}$

Consider $m:w' \in d\{\widetilde{m' : w'}\}$. By Hypothesis 3 there is $m:w \in d\{\widetilde{m : w}\}$ such that $\Sigma \vdash w \leq_{S_{alg}} w'$.

To show that $(w, w') \in R$, we need to pick some Σ' such that $(w, w') \in \Sigma'$ and $\mathbf{sound} \Sigma'$. If $(w, w') \in \Sigma$, we can just take $\Sigma' = \Sigma$. If $(w, w') \notin \Sigma$, we consider $\Sigma' = \Sigma, (w, w')$ and show that $\mathbf{sound} \Sigma'$.

Consider $(w'', w''') \in \Sigma'$. We have to show that $\Sigma' \setminus (w'', w''') \vdash w'' \leq_{S_{alg}} w'''$.

If $(w'', w''') = (w, w')$ then $\Sigma' \setminus (w, w') \vdash w \leq_{S_{alg}} w'$ holds because $\Sigma \vdash w \leq_{S_{alg}} w'$ (Hypothesis 3). Note that $\Sigma' \setminus (w, w') = \Sigma$.

If $(w'', w''') \neq (w, w')$ then $(w'', w''') \in \Sigma$. Since $\mathbf{sound} \Sigma$, we have that $\Sigma \setminus (w'', w''') \vdash w'' \leq_{S_{alg}} w'''$. Then $\Sigma' \setminus (w'', w''') \vdash w'' \leq_{S_{alg}} w'''$ holds by Lemma 57.

Therefore, $\mathbf{sound} \Sigma'$ and $(w, w') \in R$.

Condition (1.a) from Def 3 holds because $(w, w') \in R$.

Condition (1.b) from Def 3 holds directly from Hypothesis 3.

■ Case OUTPUT:

Similar to the previous case.

By satisfying all the conditions from Def 3, we have shown that R is a tpestate simulation. ◀

► **Corollary 58** (Algorithm soundness and completeness). $\emptyset \vdash w_1^{E_1} \leq_{S_{alg}} w_2^{E_2}$ if and only if $w_1^{E_1} \leq_S w_2^{E_2}$.

Proof. Follows from Theorems 8 and 9. ◀

► **Lemma 12** (Reflexivity). For all t , then $t \leq t$.

Proof. By induction on the structure of t .

■ Case $t = \top$:

Clearly, $\top \leq \top$ by the Top rule.

■ Case $t = \perp$:

Clearly, $\perp \leq \perp$ by the Bot rule.

■ Case $t = u$:

Clearly, $u \leq u$ since $u \leq_S u$ holds by Lemma 5.

■ Case $t = t_1 \cup t_2$

Induction hypotheses: $t_1 \leq t_1$ and $t_2 \leq t_2$.

$t_1 \cup t_2 \leq t_1 \cup t_2$ is derived in the following way:

$$\frac{\frac{t_1 \leq t_1}{t_1 \leq t_1 \cup t_2} \text{ UNION_R} \quad \frac{t_2 \leq t_2}{t_2 \leq t_1 \cup t_2} \text{ UNION_R}}{t_1 \cup t_2 \leq t_1 \cup t_2} \text{ UNION_L}$$

■ Case $t = t_1 \cap t_2$

Similar to the previous case.

► **Lemma 59** (Unique Top). *For all t, t' , if $\top \leq t$ then $t' \leq t$.*

Proof. By induction on the derivation $\top \leq t$.

- Case $\top \leq \top$ (Top):
Clearly $t' \leq \top$ by the Top rule.
- Case $\top \leq t_1 \cup t_2$ (Union_R where $i = 1$):
Rule premises: $\top \leq t_1$. Induction hypothesis: $t' \leq t_1$.
Therefore, $t' \leq t_1 \cup t_2$ by the Union_R rule.
- Case $\top \leq t_1 \cup t_2$ (Union_R where $i = 2$):
Similar to the previous case.
- Case $\top \leq t_1 \cap t_2$ (Intersection_R):
Rule premises: $\top \leq t_1$ and $\top \leq t_2$. Induction hypotheses: $t' \leq t_1$ and $t' \leq t_2$.
Therefore, $t' \leq t_1 \cap t_2$ by the Intersection_R rule.

► **Lemma 60** (States Transitivity). *For all u, u', t , if $u \leq u'$ and $u' \leq t$, then $u \leq t$.*

Proof. By induction on the derivation $u' \leq t$.

- Case $u' \leq \top$ (Top):
Clearly, $u \leq \top$ by the Top rule.
- Case $u' \leq u''$ (States):
If $u \leq u'$ and $u' \leq u''$, then $u \leq u''$ by Lemma 6.
- Case $u' \leq t_1 \cup t_2$ (Union_R where $i = 1$):
Rule premises: $u' \leq t_1$. Induction hypothesis: $u \leq t_1$.
Therefore, $u \leq t_1 \cup t_2$ by the Union_R rule.
- Case $u' \leq t_1 \cup t_2$ (Union_R where $i = 2$):
Similar to the previous case.
- Case $u' \leq t_1 \cap t_2$ (Intersection_R):
Similar to the previous case.

► **Lemma 13** (Transitivity). *For all t, t', t'' , if $t \leq t'$ and $t' \leq t''$, then $t \leq t''$.*

Proof. By induction on the derivation $t \leq t'$.

- Case $t \leq \top$ (Top):
Given our assumption that $\top \leq t''$, we conclude $t \leq t''$ by Lemma 59.
- Case $\perp \leq t'$ (Bot):
Clearly, $\perp \leq t''$ by the Bot rule.
- Case $u \leq u'$ (States):
Given our assumption that $u' \leq t''$, we conclude $u \leq t''$ by Lemma 60.
- Case $t_1 \cup t_2 \leq t'$ (Union_L):
Rule hypotheses: $t_1 \leq t'$ and $t_2 \leq t'$. Induction hypotheses: $t_1 \leq t''$ and $t_2 \leq t''$.
Therefore, $t_1 \cup t_2 \leq t''$ by the Union_L rule.

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- Case $t \leq t'_1 \cup t'_2$ (Union_R where $i = 1$):
 Rule premises: $t \leq t'_1$. Induction hypothesis: $\forall t'' . t'_1 \leq t'' \implies t \leq t''$.
 Recall the lemma assumption: $t'_1 \cup t'_2 \leq t''$.
 To show that $t \leq t''$, we perform again induction but on the derivation $t'_1 \cup t'_2 \leq t''$.
 - Case $t'_1 \cup t'_2 \leq \top$ (Top):
 Clearly, $t \leq \top$ by the Top rule.
 - Case $t'_1 \cup t'_2 \leq t''$ (Union_L):
 Rule premises: $t'_1 \leq t''$ and $t'_2 \leq t''$.
 Therefore, $t \leq t''$ by the (first) induction hypothesis.
 - Case $t'_1 \cup t'_2 \leq t''_1 \cup t''_2$ (Union_R where $i = 1$):
 Rule premises: $t'_1 \cup t'_2 \leq t''_1$. Induction hypothesis: $t \leq t''_1$.
 Therefore, $t \leq t''_1 \cup t''_2$ by the Union_R rule.
 - Case $t'_1 \cup t'_2 \leq t''_1 \cup t''_2$ (Union_R where $i = 2$):
 Similar to the previous case.
 - Case $t'_1 \cup t'_2 \leq t''_1 \cap t''_2$ (Intersection_R):
 Similar to the previous case.
 - Case $t \leq t'_1 \cup t'_2$ (Union_R where $i = 2$):
 Similar to the previous case.
 - Case $t \leq t'_1 \cap t'_2$ (Intersection_R):
 Similar to the previous case.
 - Case $t_1 \cap t_2 \leq t'$ (Intersection_L where $i = 1$):
 Rule hypothesis: $t_1 \leq t'$. Induction hypotheses: $t_1 \leq t''$.
 Therefore, $t_1 \cap t_2 \leq t''$ by the Intersection_L rule.
 - Case $t_1 \cap t_2 \leq t'$ (Intersection_L where $i = 2$):
 Similar to the previous case. ◀
- **Lemma 61** (Intersect Many Right). *For all t and $I \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{T})$, if for all $t' \in I$ it holds that $t \leq t'$, then $t \leq \bigcap I$.*
- Proof.** By induction on the size of I . ◀
- **Lemma 62** (Intersect Many Left). *For all t and $I \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{T})$, if there exists $t' \in I$ such that $t' \leq t$, then $\bigcap I \leq t$.*
- Proof.** By induction on the size of I . ◀
- **Lemma 63** (Union Many Right). *For all t and $U \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{T})$, if there exists $t' \in U$ such that $t \leq t'$, then $t \leq \bigcup U$.*
- Proof.** By induction on the size of U . ◀
- **Lemma 64** (Union Many Left). *For all t and $U \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{T})$, if for all $t' \in U$ it holds that $t' \leq t$, then $\bigcup U \leq t$.*
- Proof.** By induction on the size of U . ◀

- **Lemma 20** (Upcast preserves protocol membership). *For all t, c and c' , then*
 $\text{tpestates}(\text{upcast}(t, c, c')) \subseteq \text{ProtInputs}(c')$

Proof. By structural induction on t . ◀

- **Theorem 21** (Upcast Consistency). *For all t, c and c' , we have $t \leq \text{upcast}(t, c, c')$.*

Proof. By structural induction on t :

- Case $t = \top$, hence $\top \leq \top$.
- Case $t = \perp$, hence $\perp \leq \perp$.
- Case $t \in \mathcal{U}$, hence $t \leq \bigcap\{u' \in \text{ProtInputs}(c') \mid t \leq u'\}$ by Lemma 61.
- Case $t = t_1 \cap t_2$, hence $t' = t'_1 \cap t'_2$. By inductive hypothesis $t_1 \leq t'_1$ and $t_2 \leq t'_2$
 By Intersection_L: $t_1 \cap t_2 \leq t_1$ and $t_1 \cap t_2 \leq t_2$
 Therefore: $t_1 \cap t_2 \leq t_1 \leq t'_1$ and $t_1 \cap t_2 \leq t_2 \leq t'_2$
 Hence, by Intersection_R: $t_1 \cap t_2 \leq t'_1 \cap t'_2$
- Case $t = t_1 \cup t_2$, hence $t' = t'_1 \cup t'_2$. By inductive hypothesis $t_1 \leq t'_1$ and $t_2 \leq t'_2$
 By Union_R: $t'_1 \leq t'_1 \cup t'_2$ and $t'_2 \leq t'_1 \cup t'_2$
 Therefore: $t_1 \leq t'_1 \leq t'_1 \cup t'_2$ and $t_2 \leq t'_2 \leq t'_1 \cup t'_2$
 Hence, by Union_L: $t_1 \cup t_2 \leq t'_1 \cup t'_2$

- **Theorem 22** (Upcast Least Upper Bound). *For all t, t', c and c' , such that*
 $\text{tpestates}(t') \subseteq \text{ProtInputs}(c')$ *and* $t \leq t'$, *we have* $\text{upcast}(t, c, c') \leq t'$.

Proof. By induction on the inference of $t \leq t'$:

- Case $t \leq \top$ (Top):
 Clearly, $\text{upcast}(t, c, c') \leq \top$ by the *Top* rule.
- Case $\perp \leq t'$ (Bot):
 Clearly, $\text{upcast}(\perp, c, c') = \perp \leq t'$ by the *Bot* rule.
- Case $u_1 \leq u_2$ (States):
 We need to show that $\text{upcast}(u_1, c, c') \leq u_2$.
 Hence, we need to show that $\bigcap\{u' \in \text{ProtInputs}(c') \mid u_1 \leq u'\} \leq u_2$.
 Applying Lemma 62, there must be a state u'' such that $u'' \in \text{ProtInputs}(c')$ and $u_1 \leq u''$
 and $u'' \leq u_2$. This is proven by picking u_2 .
- Case $t_1 \cup t_2 \leq t'$ (Union_L):
 We have (premises of Union_L)
 1. $t_1 \leq t'$
 2. $t_2 \leq t'$
 and (Induction Hypotheses)
 3. $\text{upcast}(t_1, c, c') \leq t'$
 4. $\text{upcast}(t_2, c, c') \leq t'$
 We need to show that $\text{upcast}(t_1 \cup t_2, c, c') \leq t'$.
 Hence, we need to show that $\text{upcast}(t_1, c, c') \cup \text{upcast}(t_2, c, c') = \text{upcast}(t_1 \cup t_2, c, c') \leq t'$.
 This is proven by applying Union_L with the hypotheses 3 and 4.
- Case $t \leq t'_1 \cup t'_2$ (Union_R where $i = 1$):
 We have (premises of Union_R):
 1. $t \leq t'_1$
 and (Induction Hypothesis)
 2. $\text{upcast}(t, c, c') \leq t'_1$

We need to show that $\text{upcast}(t, c, c') \leq t'_1 \cup t'_2$.

This is proven by applying `Union_R` with the hypothesis 2.

- Case $t \leq t'_1 \cup t'_2$ (`Union_R` where $i = 2$):

Similar to the previous case.

- Case $t \leq t'_1 \cap t'_2$ (`Intersection_R`):

We have (premises of `Intersection_R`)

1. $t \leq t'_1$
2. $t \leq t'_2$

and (Induction Hypotheses)

3. $\text{upcast}(t, c, c') \leq t'_1$
4. $\text{upcast}(t, c, c') \leq t'_2$

We need to show that $\text{upcast}(t, c, c') \leq t'_1 \cap t'_2$.

This is proven by applying `Intersection_R` with the hypotheses 3 and 4.

- Case $t_1 \cap t_2 \leq t'$ (`Intersection_L` where $i = 1$):

We have (premises of `Intersection_L`)

1. $t_1 \leq t'$

and (Induction Hypothesis)

2. $\text{upcast}(t_1, c, c') \leq t'$

We need to show that $\text{upcast}(t_1 \cap t_2, c, c') \leq t'$.

Hence, we need to show that $\text{upcast}(t_1, c, c') \cap \text{upcast}(t_2, c, c') = \text{upcast}(t_1 \cap t_2, c, c') \leq t'$.

This is proven by applying `Intersection_L` with the hypothesis 2.

- Case $t_1 \cap t_2 \leq t'$ (`Intersection_L` where $i = 2$):

Similar to the previous case. ◀

► **Theorem 23** (Upcast Preserves Subtyping). *For all t, t', c and c' , such that $t \leq t'$, we have $\text{upcast}(t, c, c') \leq \text{upcast}(t', c, c')$.*

Proof. By induction on the inference of $t \leq t'$:

- Case $t \leq \top$ (`Top`):

Clearly, $\text{upcast}(t, c, c') \leq \text{upcast}(\top, c, c')$ by the *Top* rule.

- Case $\perp \leq t'$ (`Bot`):

Clearly, $\text{upcast}(\perp, c, c') = \text{upcast}(t', c, c')$ by the *Bot* rule.

- Case $u_1 \leq u_2$ (`States`):

We need to show that $\text{upcast}(u_1, c, c') \leq \text{upcast}(u_2, c, c')$.

Hence, we need to show that $\bigcap\{u' \in \text{ProtInputs}(c') \mid u_1 \leq u'\} \leq \bigcap\{u'' \in \text{ProtInputs}(c') \mid S_2 \leq u''\}$.

Applying Lemma 61, we need to show that for all states $u'' \in \text{ProtInputs}(c')$ such that $u_2 \leq u''$, we have that $\bigcap\{u' \in \text{ProtInputs}(c') \mid u_1 \leq u'\} \leq u''$.

Applying Lemma 62, we need to show that there is a state $u' \in \text{ProtInputs}(c')$ such that $u_1 \leq u'$ and $u' \leq u''$.

We can pick u' : since $u_1 \leq u_2$ and $u_2 \leq u''$, we have by transitivity that $u_1 \leq u''$, and by reflexivity we have that $u'' \leq u''$.

- Case $t_1 \cup t_2 \leq t'$ (`Union_L`):

We have (premises of `Union_L`)

1. $t_1 \leq t'$
2. $t_2 \leq t'$

and (Induction Hypotheses)

3. $\text{upcast}(t_1, c, c') \leq \text{upcast}(t', c, c')$

4. $\text{upcast}(t_2, c, c') \leq \text{upcast}(t', c, c')$

We need to show that $\text{upcast}(t_1, c, c') \cup \text{upcast}(t_2, c, c') \leq \text{upcast}(t', c, c')$.

This is proven by applying `Union_L` with the hypotheses 3 and 4.

■ Case $t \leq t'_1 \cup t'_2$ (`Union_R` where $i = 1$):

We have (premises of `Union_R`):

1. $t \leq t'_1$

and (Induction Hypothesis)

2. $\text{upcast}(t, c, c') \leq \text{upcast}(t'_1, c, c')$

We need to show that $\text{upcast}(t, c, c') \leq \text{upcast}(t'_1, c, c') \cup \text{upcast}(t'_2, c, c')$.

This is proven by applying `Union_R` with the hypothesis 2.

■ Case $t \leq t'_1 \cup t'_2$ (`Union_R` where $i = 2$):

Similar to the previous case.

■ Case $t \leq t'_1 \cap t'_2$ (`Intersection_R`):

We have (premises of `Intersection_R`)

1. $t \leq t'_1$

2. $t \leq t'_2$

and (Induction Hypotheses)

3. $\text{upcast}(t, c, c') \leq \text{upcast}(t'_1, c, c')$

4. $\text{upcast}(t, c, c') \leq \text{upcast}(t'_2, c, c')$

We need to show that $\text{upcast}(t, c, c') \leq \text{upcast}(t'_1, c, c') \cap \text{upcast}(t'_2, c, c')$.

This is proven by applying `Intersection_R` with the hypotheses 3 and 4.

■ Case $t_1 \cap t_2 \leq t'$ (`Intersection_L` where $i = 1$):

We have (premises of `Intersection_L`)

1. $t_1 \leq t'$

and (Induction Hypothesis)

2. $\text{upcast}(t_1, c, c') \leq \text{upcast}(t', c, c')$

We need to show that $\text{upcast}(t_1, c, c') \cap \text{upcast}(t_2, c, c') \leq \text{upcast}(t', c, c')$.

This is proven by applying `Intersection_L` with the hypothesis 2.

■ Case $t_1 \cap t_2 \leq t'$ (`Intersection_L` where $i = 2$):

Similar to the previous case. ◀

► **Lemma 25** (Downcast preserves protocol membership). *For all t, c and c' , we have $\text{tpestates}(\text{downcast}(t, c, c')) \subseteq \text{ProtInputs}(c')$*

Proof. By structural induction on t . ◀

► **Theorem 26** (Downcast Consistency). *For all t, c and c' , we have $\text{downcast}(t, c, c') \leq t$.*

Proof. By structural induction on t :

■ Case $t = \top$, hence $\top \leq \top$.

■ Case $t = \perp$, hence $\perp \leq \perp$.

■ Case $t \in \mathcal{U}$, hence $\bigcup\{u' \in \text{ProtInputs}(c') \mid u' \leq t\} \leq t$ by Lemma 64.

■ Case $t = t_1 \cap t_2$, hence $t' = t'_1 \cap t'_2$.

By inductive hypothesis $t'_1 \leq t_1$ and $t'_2 \leq t_2$.

Hence, $t'_1 \cap t'_2 \leq t_1 \cap t_2$ by `Intersection_R` and `Intersection_L`.

■ Case $t = t_1 \cup t_2$, hence $t' = t'_1 \cup t'_2$.

By inductive hypothesis $t'_1 \leq t_1$ and $t'_2 \leq t_2$.

Hence, $t'_1 \cup t'_2 \leq t_1 \cup t_2$ by `Union_L` and `Union_R`.

► **Theorem 27** (Downcast Greatest Lower Bound). *For all t, t', c and c' , such that $\text{typestates}(t') \subseteq \text{ProtInputs}(c')$ and $t' \leq t$, we have $t' \leq \text{downcast}(t, c, c')$.*

Proof. By induction on $t' \leq t$:

- Case $t' \leq \top$ (Top):
Clearly, $t' \leq \text{downcast}(\top, c, c')$ by the Top rule.
- Case $t' \leq \perp$ (Bot):
Clearly, $t' \leq \text{downcast}(\perp, c, c')$ by the Bot rule.
- Case $u_1 \leq u_2$ (Gay and Hole):
We need to show that $u_1 \leq \text{downcast}(u_2, c, c')$.
We need to show that $u_1 \leq \bigcup\{u' \in \text{ProtInputs}(c') \mid u' \leq u_2\}$.
Applying Lemma 63, there needs to exist a state u'' such that $u'' \in \text{ProtInputs}(c')$ and $u'' \leq u_2$ and $u_1 \leq u''$. This is proven by picking u_1 .
- Case $t'_1 \cup t'_2 \leq t$ (Union_L):
We have (premises of Union_L)
 1. $t'_1 \leq t$
 2. $t'_2 \leq t$
 and (Induction Hypotheses)
 3. $t'_1 \leq \text{downcast}(t, c, c')$
 4. $t'_2 \leq \text{downcast}(t, c, c')$
 We need to show that $t'_1 \cup t'_2 \leq \text{downcast}(t, c, c')$.
This is proven by applying Union_L with the hypotheses 3 and 4.
- Case $t' \leq t_1 \cup t_2$ (Union_R where $i = 1$):
We have (premises of Union_R)
 1. $t' \leq t_1$
 and (Induction Hypothesis)
 2. $t' \leq \text{downcast}(t_1, c, c')$
 We need to show that $t' \leq \text{downcast}(t_1 \cup t_2, c, c')$.
Hence, we need to show that $t' \leq \text{downcast}(t_1 \cup t_2, c, c') = \text{downcast}(t_1, c, c') \cup \text{downcast}(t_2, c, c')$.
This is proven by applying Union_R with the hypothesis 2.
- Case $t' \leq t_1 \cup t_2$ (Union_R where $i = 2$):
Similar to the previous case.
- Case $t' \leq t_1 \cap t_2$ (Intersection_R):
We have (premises of Intersection_R)
 1. $t' \leq t_1$
 2. $t' \leq t_2$
 and (Induction Hypotheses)
 3. $t' \leq \text{downcast}(t_1, c, c')$
 4. $t' \leq \text{downcast}(t_2, c, c')$
 We need to show that $t' \leq \text{downcast}(t_1 \cap t_2, c, c')$.
Hence, we need to show that $t' \leq \text{downcast}(t_1 \cap t_2, c, c') = \text{downcast}(t_1, c, c') \cap \text{downcast}(t_2, c, c')$.
This is proven by applying Intersection_R with the hypotheses 3 and 4.
- Case $t'_1 \cap t'_2 \leq t$ (Intersection_L where $i = 1$):
We have (premises of Intersection_L)
 1. $t'_1 \leq t$
 and (Induction Hypothesis)

2. $t'_1 \leq \text{downcast}(t, c, c')$

We need to show that $t'_1 \cap t'_2 \leq \text{downcast}(t, c, c')$.

This is proven by applying `Intersection_L` with the hypothesis 2.

■ Case $t'_1 \cap t'_2 \leq t$ (`Intersection_L` where $i = 2$):

Similar to the previous case.

► **Theorem 28** (Downcast Preserves Subtyping). *For all t, t', c and c' , such that $t \leq t'$, we have $\text{downcast}(t, c, c') \leq \text{downcast}(t', c, c')$.*

Proof. By induction on the inference of $t \leq t'$:

■ Case $t \leq \top$ (`Top`):

Clearly, $\text{downcast}(t, c, c') \leq \text{downcast}(\top, c, c')$ by the `Top` rule.

■ Case $\perp \leq t'$ (`Bot`):

Clearly, $\text{downcast}(\perp, c, c') = \text{downcast}(t', c, c')$ by the `Bot` rule.

■ Case $u_1 \leq u_2$ (`States`):

We need to show that $\text{downcast}(u_1, c, c') \leq \text{downcast}(u_2, c, c')$.

We need to show that $\bigcup\{u' \in \text{ProtInputs}(c') \mid u' \leq u_1\} \leq \bigcup\{u'' \in \text{ProtInputs}(c') \mid u'' \leq u_2\}$.

Applying Lemma 64, we need to show that for all states $u' \in \text{ProtInputs}(c')$ such that $u' \leq u_1$, we have that $u' \leq \bigcup\{u'' \in \text{ProtInputs}(c') \mid u'' \leq u_2\}$.

Applying Lemma 63, we need to show that there is a state $u'' \in \text{ProtInputs}(c')$ such that $u'' \leq u_2$ and $u' \leq u''$.

We can pick u' : since $u_1 \leq u_2$ and $u' \leq u_1$, we have by transitivity that $u' \leq u_2$, and by reflexivity we have that $u' \leq u'$.

■ Case $t_1 \cup t_2 \leq t'$ (`Union_L`):

We have (premises of `Union_L`)

1. $t_1 \leq t'$

2. $t_2 \leq t'$

and (Induction Hypotheses)

3. $\text{downcast}(t_1, c, c') \leq \text{downcast}(t', c, c')$

4. $\text{downcast}(t_2, c, c') \leq \text{downcast}(t', c, c')$

We need to show that $\text{downcast}(t_1, c, c') \cup \text{downcast}(t_2, c, c') \leq \text{downcast}(t', c, c')$.

This is proven by applying `Union_L` with the hypotheses 3 and 4.

■ Case $t \leq t'_1 \cup t'_2$ (`Union_R` where $i = 1$):

We have (premises of `Union_R`):

1. $t \leq t'_1$

and (Induction Hypothesis)

2. $\text{downcast}(t, c, c') \leq \text{downcast}(t'_1, c, c')$

We need to show that $\text{downcast}(t, c, c') \leq \text{downcast}(t'_1, c, c') \cup \text{downcast}(t'_2, c, c')$.

This is proven by applying `Union_R` with the hypothesis 2.

■ Case $t \leq t'_1 \cup t'_2$ (`Union_R` where $i = 2$):

Similar to the previous case.

■ Case $t \leq t'_1 \cap t'_2$ (`Intersection_R`):

We have (premises of `Intersection_R`)

1. $t \leq t'_1$

2. $t \leq t'_2$

and (Induction Hypotheses)

3. $\text{downcast}(t, c, c') \leq \text{downcast}(t'_1, c, c')$

4. $\text{downcast}(t, c, c') \leq \text{downcast}(t'_2, c, c')$

We need to show that $\text{downcast}(t, c, c') \leq \text{downcast}(t'_1, c, c') \cap \text{downcast}(t'_2, c, c')$.

This is proven by applying `Intersection_R` with the hypotheses 3 and 4.

■ Case $t_1 \cap t_2 \leq t'$ (`Intersection_L` where $i = 1$):

We have (premises of `Intersection_L`)

1. $t_1 \leq t'$

and (Induction Hypothesis)

2. $\text{downcast}(t_1, c, c') \leq \text{downcast}(t', c, c')$

We need to show that $\text{downcast}(t_1, c, c') \cap \text{downcast}(t_2, c, c') \leq \text{downcast}(t', c, c')$.

This is proven by applying `Intersection_L` with the hypothesis 2.

■ Case $t_1 \cap t_2 \leq t'$ (`Intersection_L` where $i = 2$):

Similar to the previous case. ◀

► **Corollary 29** (Downcast reverses upcast). *For all t, c and c' , we have*
 $t \leq \text{downcast}(\text{upcast}(t, c, c'), c', c)$.

Proof. We know by Theorem 21 that $t \leq \text{upcast}(t, c, c')$.

Let $t' = \text{upcast}(t, c, c')$.

Since $t \leq t'$ and $\text{tpestates}(t) \subseteq \text{ProtInputs}(c)$, then, by Theorem 27, $t \leq \text{downcast}(t', c', c)$.

Thus, $t \leq \text{upcast}(\text{downcast}(t', c', c), c', c)$. ◀

► **Corollary 30** (Upcast reverses downcast). *For all t, c and c' , we have*
 $\text{upcast}(\text{downcast}(t, c, c'), c', c) \leq t$.

Proof. We know by Theorem 26 that $\text{downcast}(t, c, c') \leq t$.

Let $t' = \text{downcast}(t, c, c')$.

Since $t' \leq t$ and $\text{tpestates}(t) \subseteq \text{ProtInputs}(c)$, then, by Theorem 22, $\text{upcast}(t', c', c) \leq t$.

Thus, $\text{upcast}(\text{downcast}(t', c', c), c', c) \leq t'$. ◀

► **Lemma 32** (Evolve preserves protocol membership). *For all t, m, o, c ,*

$\text{tpestates}(t) \subseteq \text{ProtInputs}(c)$ *implies* $\text{tpestates}(\text{evolve}(t, m, o)) \subseteq \text{ProtInputs}(c)$

Proof. By structural induction on t . ◀

► **Theorem 33** (Evolve preserves subtyping). *For all t and t' such that $t \leq t'$, we have that*
 $\text{evolve}(t, m, o) \leq \text{evolve}(t', m, o)$

Proof. By induction on $t \leq t'$. ◀

► **Theorem 34** (Evolve and upcast). *For all t, m, o, c and c' , we have that*
 $\text{upcast}(\text{evolve}(t, m, o), c, c') \leq \text{evolve}(\text{upcast}(t, c, c'), m, o)$

Proof. By structural induction on t . ◀

► **Theorem 35** (Evolve and downcast). *For all t, m, o, c and c' , we have that*
 $\text{evolve}(\text{downcast}(t, c, c'), m, o) \leq \text{downcast}(\text{evolve}(t, m, o), c, c')$

Proof. By structural induction on t . ◀

► **Theorem 40** (Typestate Trees Well-formedness Preserved By Upcast). *For all c'' , tt , such that $\vdash tt$ and $c\mathbb{1}(tt) \leq_C c''$, it holds that $\vdash \text{upcastTT}(tt, c'')$.*

Proof. Let $tt = (c, t, tts)$. We do induction on the distance between c and c'' .

- Case $c = c''$
Thus, $\text{upcastTT}(tt, c'') = tt$ and so $\vdash \text{upcastTT}(tt, c'')$.
- Case $c \neq c''$
Let $c' = \text{Super}(c)$.
By Def. 39 $\text{upcastTT}(tt, c'') = \text{upcastTT}((c', \text{upcast}(t, c, c'), \{tt\}), c'')$
Induction Hypothesis: If $\vdash (c', \text{upcast}(t, c, c'), \{tt\})$ then $\vdash \text{upcastTT}(tt, c'')$
We know:
 1. By Lemma 20 that $\text{tpestates}(\text{upcast}(t, c, c')) \subseteq \text{ProtInputs}(c')$;
 2. By hypothesis that $\vdash tt$;
 3. By Theorem 21 that $t \leq \text{upcast}(t, c, c')$.
By Def 38, $\vdash (c', \text{upcast}(t, c, c'), \{tt\})$ since $\text{upcast}(t, c, c') \leq \text{upcast}(t, c, c')$ and $\vdash tt$.
By the induction hypothesis we get $\vdash \text{upcastTT}(tt, c'')$.

◀

► **Lemma 42** (Closest correctness). *For all tt and c , if $c \leq_C c\mathbb{1}(tt)$ then $c \leq_C c\mathbb{1}(\text{closestSubT}(tt, c))$.*

Proof. By induction on the distance between $c\mathbb{1}(tt)$ and c .

◀

► **Lemma 65** (Typestate Trees Well-formedness Preserved by Closest). *For all c , tt such that $\vdash tt$, it holds that $\vdash \text{closestSubT}(c, tt)$.*

Proof. By structural induction on tt .

◀

► **Theorem 44** (Typestate Trees Well-formedness Preserved By Downcast). *For all c , tt , such that $\vdash tt$ and $c \leq_C c\mathbb{1}(tt)$, it holds that $\vdash \text{downcastTT}(tt, c)$.*

Proof. Let $tt = (c', t, tts)$ and $tt' = \text{closestSubT}(c, tt)$. Proof by cases:

- Case $c = c'$
Thus, $\vdash tt'$ by Lemma 65.
- Case $c \neq c'$.
By Def. 43, $\text{downcastTT}(tt, c) = (c, \text{downcast}(\text{ty}(tt'), c\mathbb{1}(tt'), c), \{\})$, a typestate tree with no children (i.e. leaf).
We know by Lemma 25 that $\text{tpestates}(\text{downcast}(\text{ty}(tt'), c\mathbb{1}(tt'), c)) \subseteq \text{ProtInputs}(c)$.
Thus, by Def. 38, $\vdash \text{downcastTT}(tt, c)$.

◀

► **Theorem 46** (Typestate Trees Well-formedness Preserved By Evolve). *For all tt , m , o , such that $\vdash tt$, it holds that $\vdash \text{evolveTT}(tt, m, o)$.*

Proof. Let tt be (c, t, tts) . Proof by induction on tt .

Induction hypothesis: $\forall tt' \in tts . \vdash tt' \Rightarrow \vdash \text{evolveTT}(tt', m, o)$.

By Def. 45, $\text{evolveTT}((c, t, tts), m, o) = (c, \text{evolve}(t, m, o), \bigcup_{tt_i \in tts} \text{evolveTT}(tt_i, m, o))$.

We know by hypothesis $\vdash (c, t, tts)$ and Def. 38 that:

1. $\text{tpestates}(t) \subseteq \text{ProtInputs}(c)$;
2. $\forall tt_i \in tts . \text{Super}(tt_i) = c$;

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3. $\forall tt_i \in tts . \text{upcast}(\text{ty}(tt_i), \text{cl}(tt_i), c) \leq t$;
4. $\forall tt_i \in tts . \vdash tt_i$.

We also know:

- By Lemma 32 and (1) that $\text{tpestates}(\text{evolve}(t, m, o)) \subseteq \text{ProtInputs}(c)$;
- Since evolveTT keeps the class and (2) that $\forall tt_i \in tts . \text{Super}(\text{evolveTT}(tt_i, m, o)) = c$;
- By Lemma 33 and (3) that $\forall tt_i \in tts . \text{evolve}(\text{upcast}(\text{ty}(tt_i), \text{cl}(tt_i), c), m, o) \leq \text{evolve}(t, m, o)$;
- By Lemma 34 that

$$\forall tt_i \in tts . \text{upcast}(\text{evolve}(\text{ty}(tt_i), m, o), \text{cl}(tt_i), c) \leq \text{evolve}(\text{upcast}(\text{ty}(tt_i), \text{cl}(tt_i), c), m, o)$$

By Transitivity (Def. 13) on the last two facts, $\forall tt_i \in tts . \text{upcast}(\text{evolve}(\text{ty}(tt_i), m, o), \text{cl}(tt_i), c) \leq \text{evolve}(t, m, o)$.

By induction hypothesis, $\forall tt_i \in tts . \vdash \text{evolveTT}(tt_i, m, o)$.

Thus, by Def 38, $\vdash \text{evolveTT}((c, t, tts), m, o)$. ◀

► **Theorem 51** (Typestate Trees Well-formedness Preserved By Merge). *For all tt, tt' , such that $\text{cl}(tt) = \text{cl}(tt')$, $\vdash tt$, and $\vdash tt'$, it holds that $\vdash \text{mrgTT}(tt, tt')$.*

Proof. Proof by induction on $\text{height}(tt) + \text{height}(tt')$.

Let $tt = (c, t, tts)$. Let $tt' = (c, t', tts')$.

Inductive hypothesis 1: $\forall tt'', tt''' . \text{height}(tt'') + \text{height}(tt''') < \text{height}(tt) + \text{height}(tt') \wedge \text{cl}(tt'') = \text{cl}(tt''') \wedge \vdash tt'' \wedge \vdash tt''' \Rightarrow \vdash \text{mrgTT}(tt'', tt''')$.

Let $tts_1 = \bigcup_{c_i \in \text{class}(tts) \cap \text{class}(tts')} \text{mrgTT}(\text{find}(c_i, tts), \text{find}(c_i, tts'))$.

Let $tts_2 = \bigcup_{c_i \in \text{class}(tts) \setminus \text{class}(tts')} \text{mrgTT}(\text{find}(c_i, tts), (c_i, \text{downcast}(t', c, c_i), \{\}))$.

Let $tts_3 = \bigcup_{c_i \in \text{class}(tts') \setminus \text{class}(tts)} \text{mrgTT}((c_i, \text{downcast}(t, c, c_i), \{\}), \text{find}(c, tts'))$.

Let $U = tts_1 \cup tts_2 \cup tts_3$.

By Def. 50, $\text{mrgTT}((c, t, tts), (c, t', tts')) = (c, t \cup t', U)$.

To show that $\vdash \text{mrgTT}(tt, tt')$, we have to prove:

1. $\text{tpestates}(t \cup t') \subseteq \text{ProtInputs}(c)$
2. $\text{nodup } U$
3. $\forall tt \in U . \text{Super}(\text{cl}(tt)) = c \wedge \text{upcast}(\text{ty}(tt), \text{cl}(tt), c) \leq t \cup t' \wedge \vdash tt$

Statement (1) is straightforward to show given Def. 18.

Statement (2) is straightforward to observe given the way U is constructed and the fact that mrgTT yields a typestate tree with the same root class as the given tree.

Now we proceed to prove (3) by induction on U :

- Case $U = \{\}$.
In this case, (3) is vacuously true.
- Case $U = \{tt_u\} \cup U'$ where $U' = U \setminus \{tt_u\}$ and $tt_u = (c_u, t_u, tts_u)$.
Induction hypothesis 2:

$$\forall tt'_u \in U' . \text{Super}(\text{cl}(tt'_u)) = c \wedge \text{upcast}(\text{ty}(tt'_u), \text{cl}(tt'_u), c) \leq t \cup t' \wedge \vdash tt'_u$$

To complete the proof, we have to show that:

1. $\text{Super}(c_u) = c$;
2. $\text{upcast}(t_u, c_u, c) \leq t \cup t'$;
3. $\vdash tt_u$.

Given that $c_u \in \text{class}(tts \cup tts')$, and since tts and tts' contain the children of tt and tt' , respectively, it is straightforward to show that (1) $\text{Super}(c_u) = c$.

Now we focus on showing that $\text{upcast}(t_u, c_u, c) \leq t \cup t'$ and $\vdash tt_u$.

We proceed by cases:

- Case $c_u \in \text{class}(tts) \wedge c_u \in \text{class}(tts')$.
 By definition: $tt_u = (c_u, t_u, tts_u) = \text{mrgTT}(\text{find}(c_u, tts), \text{find}(c_u, tts'))$.
 By Def. 50, $t_u = \text{ty}(\text{find}(c_u, tts)) \cup \text{ty}(\text{find}(c_u, tts'))$.
 Since $\vdash tt$, by Def. 38, then $\text{upcast}(\text{ty}(\text{find}(c_u, tts)), c_u, c) \leq t$.
 Since $\vdash tt'$, by Def. 38, then $\text{upcast}(\text{ty}(\text{find}(c_u, tts')), c_u, c) \leq t'$.
 By Def. 19, $\text{upcast}(t_u, c_u, c) = \text{upcast}(\text{ty}(\text{find}(c_u, tts)), c_u, c) \cup \text{upcast}(\text{ty}(\text{find}(c_u, tts')), c_u, c)$.
 By Union_L and Union_R, we have that $\text{upcast}(t_u, c_u, c) \leq t \cup t'$.
 Since $\text{find}(c_u, tts)$ yields a child of tt , and $\text{find}(c_u, tts')$ yields a child of tt' , we know:
 - * $\text{height}(\text{find}(c_u, tts)) + \text{height}(\text{find}(c_u, tts')) < \text{height}(tt) + \text{height}(tt')$;
 - * $\text{cl}(\text{find}(c_u, tts)) = \text{cl}(\text{find}(c_u, tts')) = c_u$;
 - * By hypotheses $\vdash tt$ and $\vdash tt'$, that $\vdash \text{find}(c_u, tts)$ and that $\vdash \text{find}(c_u, tts')$.
 By induction hypothesis 1, $\vdash tt_u$.
 Thus, we conclude that $\text{upcast}(t_u, c_u, c) \leq t \cup t'$ and $\vdash tt_u$.
- Case $c_i \in \text{class}(tts) \wedge c_u \notin \text{class}(tts')$.
 By the definition: $tt_u = (c_u, t_u, tts_u) = \text{mrgTT}(\text{find}(c_u, tts), (c_u, \text{downcast}(t', c, c_u), \{\}))$.
 By Def. 50, $t_u = \text{ty}(\text{find}(c_u, tts)) \cup \text{downcast}(t', c, c_u)$.
 Since $\vdash tt$, by Def. 38, then $\text{upcast}(\text{ty}(\text{find}(c_u, tts)), c_u, c) \leq t$.
 By Lemma 30, $\text{upcast}(\text{downcast}(t', c, c_u), c_u, c) \leq t'$.
 By Def. 19, $\text{upcast}(t_u, c_u, c) = \text{upcast}(\text{ty}(\text{find}(c_u, tts)), c_u, c) \cup \text{upcast}(\text{downcast}(t', c, c_u), c_u, c)$.
 By Union_L and Union_R, we have that $\text{upcast}(t_u, c_u, c) \leq t \cup t'$.
 Since $\text{find}(c_u, tts)$ yields a child of tt , we know:
 - * $\text{height}(\text{find}(c_u, tts)) + \text{height}((c_u, \text{downcast}(t', c, c_u), \{\})) < \text{height}(tt) + \text{height}(tt')$;
 - * $\text{cl}(\text{find}(c_u, tts)) = \text{cl}((c_u, \text{downcast}(t', c, c_u), \{\})) = c_u$;
 - * By hypothesis $\vdash tt$, that $\vdash \text{find}(c_u, tts)$;
 - * By Def. 38 that $\vdash (c_u, \text{downcast}(t', c, c_u), \{\})$.
 By induction hypothesis 1, $\vdash tt_u$.
 Thus, we conclude that $\text{upcast}(t_u, c_u, c) \leq t \cup t'$ and $\vdash tt_u$.
- Case $c_u \notin \text{class}(tts) \wedge c_u \in \text{class}(tts')$.
 Similar to the previous case.

Given $\text{Super}(c_u) = c \wedge \text{upcast}(t_u, c_u, c) \leq t \cup t' \wedge \vdash tt_u$ and the induction hypothesis 2, we get that $\forall tt \in U$. $\text{Super}(\text{cl}(tt)) = c \wedge \text{upcast}(\text{ty}(tt), \text{cl}(tt), c) \leq t \cup t' \wedge \vdash tt$.

Thus, $\vdash \text{mrgTT}(tt_1, tt_2)$. ◀

► **Lemma 66** (Typestate Trees Soundness Preserved By Closest). *For all c, t, c', tt , such that $\vdash_{c,t} tt$ and $c' \leq_C \text{cl}(tt)$, it holds that $\vdash_{c,t} \text{closestSubT}(c', tt)$.*

Proof. By structural induction on tt . ◀

► **Theorem 54** (Typestate Trees Soundness Preservation). *Soundness is preserved by:*

upcast – for all c, t, c', tt , such that $\vdash_{c,t} tt$ and $\text{cl}(tt) \leq_C c'$, it holds that

$$\vdash_{c,t} \text{upcastTT}(tt, c')$$

downcast – for all c, t, c', tt , such that $\vdash_{c,t} tt$ and $c \leq_C c' \leq_C \text{cl}(tt)$, it holds that

$$\vdash_{c,t} \text{downcastTT}(tt, c')$$

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evolve – for all c, t, tt, m, o , such that $\vdash_{c,t} tt$, it holds that

$$\vdash_{c, \text{evolve}(t,m,o)} \text{evolveTT}(tt, m, o)$$

merge – for all c, t, tt_1, tt_2 , such that $\vdash_{c,t} tt_1$ or $\vdash_{c,t} tt_2$, and $\text{cl}(tt_1) = \text{cl}(tt_2)$, it holds that $\vdash_{c,t} \text{mrgTT}(tt_1, tt_2)$.

Proof. The proof of soundness preservation for each tpestate tree operation proceeds in the following way:

- **upcast** – By induction on the distance between $\text{cl}(tt)$ and c' ;
- **downcast** – By Lemma 66 and cases on the definition of **downcast**;
- **evolve** – By structural induction on tt ;
- **merge** – By induction on $\text{height}(tt) + \text{height}(tt')$.

